

Review

Allosteric antibodies: a novel paradigm in drug discovery

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Allostery represents a fundamental mechanism in protein regulation, enabling modulation of protein function from sites distal to the active site. While traditionally explored in the context of small molecules, allosteric modulation is gaining traction as a main mode of action in the realm of antibodies, which offer enhanced specificity and reduced toxicity. This review delves into the rapidly growing field of allosteric antibodies, highlighting recent therapeutic advancements and novel druggability avenues. We also explore the potential of these antibodies as innovative tools in drug discovery and discuss contemporary strategies for designing novel allosteric antibodies, leveraging state-of-the-art computational approaches.

Allostery and antibodies

As an omnipresent mechanism, allostery regulates protein functional dynamics [1]. Targeting allosteric sites, which results in perturbation of protein conformational dynamics, offers an alternative way to modulate molecular function [2,3]. Recognizing the need to explore new paradigms to overcome drug resistance and address target space limitations [4], researchers are exploring allostery as an appealing modality [5]. While small molecules have traditionally been reported as allosteric modulators, and peptides have emerged more recently [6], antibodies might offer distinct advantages [7].

Antibodies are macromolecules that have had a tremendous impact on treatments, with more than 160 of them approved by health authorities worldwide for various therapeutic areas [8]. Compared with other drugs, antibodies present a higher selectivity profile due to their large binding site. Their solubility makes them suitable for targeting both membrane-bound and soluble proteins. In addition, they have a longer half-life and can mediate **effector functions** (see [Glossary](#)) [8]. Christopoulos and colleagues included antibodies as allosteric modulators, shedding light on novel allosteric modulations [9]. In this review, we propose specific definitions and a novel vocabulary for allosteric antibodies ([Box 1](#)).

We provide here a comprehensive overview of emerging opportunities and paradigms associated with allosteric antibodies. Starting from historical perspectives, this review highlights potential novel avenues for druggability and new formats. Beyond therapeutic applications, we also present their role as tools in the broader context of drug discovery. We also propose a roadmap for the future design of antibodies targeting a relevant allosteric site thanks to recent progress of modern computational methods.

Allosteric antibodies: a novel druggability avenue

The exploration of allosteric antibodies has opened new frontiers in drug discovery and therapeutic development. By targeting allosteric sites, these antibodies offer an innovative mechanism for modulating protein function, advancing treatments for various diseases.

Highlights

A novel pharmacology is emerging that enables precise regulation of protein activity through antibody binding to allosteric sites/epitopes, paving the way for a deeper understanding of allosteric regulations of target proteins.

Successful discoveries of allosteric antibodies against previously antibody-undruggable targets, such as G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) or ligand-gated ion channels, are shedding light on potential new druggability avenues with antibodies.

Allosteric antibodies are also of interest for small molecules discovery, opening up a new era by integrating the two technologies.

Recent efforts in the fields of computational biology and artificial intelligence (AI) hold promise for integrating allosteric site detection with *de novo* antibody design, paving the way for efficient allosteric antibody discovery.

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Box 1. Definitions related to allosteric antibodies

Allosterism has started and evolved within the world of small molecules [2]. However, antibodies are structurally and mechanistically different drugs [8]. Therefore, a novel vocabulary is desired to describe antibodies that act via binding to an allosteric site/epitope and their effects [9].

An allosteric site/epitope is by definition a protein region topographically distinct from the ligand-binding one [2]. Worth noting, because antibodies are large molecules, steric hindrance, which appears if an antibody binds very close to the ligand binding residues and obstructs them because of its size, would not be considered as allosterism. In addition, binding of an antibody to residues belonging to the ligand-binding site, even when these are in an inactive conformation, is also not regarded as allosterism. Furthermore, allosterism is an intrinsic property of all proteins, not only receptors or enzymes but also protein ligands which can be targeted by antibodies.

We propose the following definitions:

An allosteric antibody is an antibody that binds to the target on a site/epitope that does not overlap or sterically overlap with the ligand binding site and which subsequently has an impact on the structural dynamics of the target, ultimately modulating its binding and/or activity.

A negative allosteric antibody modulator (NAAM) is an antibody that stabilizes and promotes a conformation which is unfavorable for binding of a ligand, a receptor, or a co-receptor, and/or for the activity (signaling).

A positive allosteric antibody modulator (PAAM) is an antibody that stabilizes and promotes a conformation favorable for binding of a ligand, a receptor, or a co-receptor, and/or for the activity (signaling).

Antibody-mediated allosteric effects are effects on the target protein that result in the binding of an antibody to an allosteric site/epitope, which has an impact on its functional dynamics. These effects encompass: modulation of the conformation in an active/inactive state, activation/inhibition of the activity, enhancement/inhibition of the binding to a partner (ligand, receptor, co-receptor) including dimerization, internalization of the target, or even disassembly of the target.

Historical perspective

Key milestones in the development of European Medicines Agency (EMA) and/or FDA-approved therapeutic antibodies have transformed the understanding of allosteric mechanisms in both immunology and oncology areas (Figure 1).

The first approved antibody, muromonab-CD3 (OKT3), was introduced in 1986 [10]. It targets the epsilon unit of CD3, which is part of the T cell receptor (TCR) on the surface of T cells [11]. The TCR, a protein complex, recognizes antigens and plays a central role in T cell-mediated immune response and the activation of immunocompetent T cells [12]. However, dysregulated, activated immunocompetent T cells have been implicated in autoimmune conditions. CD3 is not implicated in TCR-mediated recognition of antigens but rather in signal transduction [12]. In addition, recent biochemical studies showed that muromonab-CD3 does not compete with the newly discovered inhibitory ligand of CD3 [12]. Instead, crystal studies revealed binding of muromonab-CD3 to a conformational epitope of CD3 [11], which prevents antigen recognition in an allosteric manner through crosslinking and subsequent internalization of the antibody–receptor complex (Figure 1). The selective removal of the TCR by internalization suppresses T cell cytotoxic functions and promotes a non-immunocompetent T cell state [10].

A decade after the approval of muromonab-CD3 for prevention of organ rejection [10], antibodies started to be approved for oncology applications. HER2, a transmembrane receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK), is often overexpressed by cancer cells and contributes to growth and proliferation [13]. Although no ligand has been identified for HER2 yet, it is commonly inferred, based on its similarity to other receptors of the same family, that its extracellular binding site corresponds to the cleft between domains I and III. Antibodies targeting HER2 have been developed, including trastuzumab (Herceptin) and pertuzumab (Perjeta) [13]. Structural data uncovered binding of trastuzumab to domain IV while pertuzumab targets the dimerization interface (domain II)

Glossary

Antibody–drug conjugate (ADC): an antibody covalently attached to a drug also called a payload.

Artificial intelligence (AI): a branch of computer science focusing on creating systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence.

Biologic: a drug derived from a biological source (e.g., antibody).

Blockbuster: a drug that generates annual sales over \$1 billion.

Chimeric antigen receptor T cell (CAR T cell): a therapeutic approach in which a patient's T cells are modified to recognize cells expressing a particular antigen.

Degrader–antibody conjugate (DAC): an antibody covalently attached to a drug called PROTAC.

Effector functions: organism defense response mediated by an antibody.

High-throughput screening (HTS): the automated testing of many compounds for desired properties.

Immune checkpoint: a signal that regulates the immune system.

Machine learning (ML): a branch of AI that focuses on designing algorithms capable of learning from data and making predictions or decisions based on these data.

Molecular dynamics (MD): a computational simulation method that studies the physical movements of atoms and molecules over time providing insights into the structural and dynamic properties of molecular systems under various conditions.

Natural killer (NK) cell engager: a class of antibodies engineered to bring in close proximity and redirect natural killer cells (immune cells) toward tumor cells.

Proteolysis-targeting chimera (PROTAC): a bifunctional molecule that brings the target protein to the protein degradation system.

T cell engager: a class of antibodies engineered to bring in close proximity and redirect T cells (immune cells) toward tumor cells.

Figure 1. Key milestones in the development of allosteric antibodies. (A) Muromonab-CD3 was the first approved therapeutic antibody. It binds CD3, part of the T cell receptor (TCR), on the surface of T cells [11]. CD3 is not implicated in TCR-mediated antigen recognition. Muromonab-CD3 induces internalization of the TCR, which leads to non-immunocompetent T cells [10]. (B) Trastuzumab targets HER2, a growth factor receptor overexpressed by many tumor cells. Trastuzumab binds to domain IV, distant from the ligand-binding site [14]. It impedes HER2 dimerization, inhibits its signaling, and promotes the internalization of the complex [16]. (C) T cell engagers are bispecific antibodies that can simultaneously bind CD3 and a tumor-associated antigen (TAA) [18,19]. These molecules activate T cells independently of TCR-recognition and engage them toward tumor cells. An IgG format is shown as an example; however, several formats of bispecific antibodies have been developed. (D) Antibody–drug conjugate (ADC) based on trastuzumab moiety binds HER2 on tumor cells which promotes the internalization of the complex and the subsequent release of the toxic payload. (E) VHH. The first approved VHH, caplacizumab, binds to an allosteric site and stabilizes the inactive conformation of the von Willebrand factor (vWF) [26]. The vWF is thus unable to bind the glycoprotein Ib (GPIb) on platelet cells. (F) Sotrovimab binds to the spike protein of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) at a site distal from its receptor (ACE2) [29]. Molecular dynamics (MD) studies revealed allosteric perturbations within the spike protein, impeding binding of a cofactor, thereby neutralizing the infection [32,33]. Created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

[14,15]. Cell-based assays highlighted that HER2-targeted antibodies negatively affect HER2-dimerization and subsequent signaling and promote internalization of the antibody–receptor complex (Figure 1) [16,17]. These inhibitory antibodies can be qualified as allosteric antibodies due to their non-ligand-competitive inhibition of HER2 [9].

The 2010s marked the debut of a novel antibody format termed bispecific, due to the fact that they can bind to two distinct targets [18,19]. The majority of bispecific antibodies are classified as **T cell engagers** [18,19]. They can simultaneously bind to the CD3 part of the TCR on T cells and to a tumor-associated antigen (TAA) on cancer cells [18,19]. Bispecific antibodies redirect T cells toward tumor cells. Preclinical models revealed that these bispecific antibodies function as conditional agonists, with T cell activation dependent on simultaneous binding to CD3 and the TAA [20–22]. T cells are activated through a mechanism independent of the antigen-binding domain of the TCR, relying on binding to CD3, an allosteric site of the TCR (Figure 1). This bispecific format does not lead to an internalization of the receptor but can mediate activation signaling. A prominent example would be the **blockbuster** epcoritamab (Epkinly), which targets CD3 on T cells and CD20 on B cells and is approved for the treatment of B cell malignancies [20].

Later in the same decade, a new era of **antibody–drug conjugate (ADC)** formats emerged [23]. ADCs are a novel category of antibody therapeutics that carry a cytotoxic payload [23]. They target membrane-bound proteins that are rapidly internalized, allowing the intracellular release of the toxic payload, which eventually leads to the elimination of the target-expressing cells [23]. HER2 targeting ADCs, which are based on trastuzumab, act via an allosteric mechanism of action. As discussed earlier, trastuzumab binds to an allosteric site of HER2, which promotes the internalization of the antibody–receptor complex (Figure 1) [14]. Consequently, trastuzumab-based ADCs have been developed and approved, like trastuzumab deruxtecan (Enhertu), for the treatment of certain types of tumors that express HER2 [24].

A novel format has been further approved based on small variable domains of camelid antibodies termed VHH (Variable Heavy domain of Heavy chain). The first VHH-based therapeutic agent, caplacizumab (Cablivi), binds the von Willebrand factor (vWF), a blood glycoprotein that promotes platelet adhesion [25]. There is an autoimmune blood disorder associated with the vWF which leads to thrombosis. Structural studies revealed that caplacizumab stabilized an inactive conformation of the vWF for platelet adhesion via binding to a site distinct from the platelet-receptor glycoprotein Ib, preventing the development of life-threatening thrombosis (Figure 1) [26,27].

The recent coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic associated with the virus severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), prompted the profiling of a diverse panel of antibodies targeting the spike protein of the viral capsid [28]. Notably, sotrovimab (Xevudy) targets the receptor-binding domain without overlapping with the receptor (ACE2) binding site (Figure 1) [29]. This close proximity disrupts post-attachment conformational changes, thereby neutralizing the infection [28–31]. Extensive computational efforts, notably **molecular dynamics (MD)** studies, revealed that sotrovimab induces allosteric perturbations within the spike protein by binding to a known allosteric site [32–35]. Additionally, sotrovimab binds to an epitope that is less sensitive to mutations, facilitating the neutralization of other SARS-CoV-2 spike mutant proteins [30,31,36]. These studies represent the first global efforts in combining computational and experimental approaches to rapidly discover, develop, and characterize neutralizing allosteric antibodies.

Major milestones for antibody therapeutics have been associated with targeting allosteric sites. Recent experimental and computational approaches elucidated the allosteric mechanism of action for exploratory targets that were deemed undruggable for antibodies, shedding light on novel druggability avenues.

GPCRs and ligand-gated ion channels (LGICs): new strides in targeting transmembrane receptors

GPCRs and LGICs are the two most common drug targets [37]. However, despite extensive efforts, few antibodies have been reported to target these membrane-embedded protein classes.

GPCRs constitute the primary targets for drug treatments, with approximately one-third of approved drugs targeting them [37]. However, only three of these drugs are antibodies [38]. This unmet gap arises from the small, accessible extracellular domains of GPCRs which are also a particularly difficult-to-express protein class [39].

Scholler and colleagues reported the discovery of a VHH-based positive allosteric modulator of a GPCR: mGlu2 [40]. The mGlu receptor family is a class C GPCR activated by a neurotransmitter called metabotropic glutamate [38]. These receptors are promising targets for brain-related diseases for which VHHs might represent alternative drugs [38]. Structural studies revealed binding of the mGlu2-targeted VHH to the Venus Flytrap (VFT) lobe and an overall stabilization of the

active form of the receptor (Figure 2), thereby exhibiting an agonistic activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* [40,41]. This structure differs from the inactive form of mGlu (Figure 2). Moreover, the VFT domain hosts a prominent allosteric site for mGlu receptors. Other allosteric antibodies targeting this domain were also reported for mGlu4 [42], mGlu5 [43], and mGlu7 [44]. Interestingly, the antibody targeting mGlu7 displays a negative cooperativity with orthosteric and allosteric agonists by promoting the internalization of the active receptor complex [44].

Additionally, a recent report describes an allosteric antibody inhibiting the calcium sensing receptor (CaSR) [45]. CaSR is another class C GPCR that senses calcium concentrations *in vivo*.

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Figure 2. Illustrations of conformational changes elicited by antibody binding to an allosteric site of the target protein. (A) mGlu2. Left panel: structure [Protein Data Bank (PDB): 7E9G] of the mGlu2 active dimer (in purple) with G protein and Variable Heavy domain of Heavy chain (VHHs) (in red). Right panel: structure (PDB: 7EPA) of the mGlu2 inactive dimer (in purple). The active form with VHHs exhibits a 90° twist from the inactive form, facilitating the G protein recruitment [40,41]. (B) IL-18Rβ. Left panel: structure (PDB: 6KN9) of IL-18Rβ (in purple) in complex with the single-chain variable fragment (scFv; in red). Right panel: structure (PDB: 3WO4) of IL-18Rβ (in purple) in complex with IL-18 (in blue) and IL-18Rα (in cyan). The scFv-bound IL-18Rβ bent opposite to the IL-18:IL-18Rα-bound IL-18Rβ complex, impacting the formation of the complex [55]. (C) Norovirus capsid protein. Left panel: structure (PDB: 8G0W) of the capsid protein GII.4.P domains (in purple) in complex with the VHH (in red). Right panel: structure (7JIE) of the viral protein GII.P.4 domain (in purple). The VHH induces subtle conformational changes along the structure of the viral capsid protein, leading to disassembly [58]. (d) 4-1BB. Left panel: structure (PDB: 6MHR) of 4-1BB (in purple) in complex with the Fab fragment of urelumab (in red). Right panel: structure (PDB: 6MPG) of 4-1BB (in purple) in complex with 4-1BBL (in cyan). The Fab-bound complex shows increased bending and agonist properties [62]. 3D structures were generated with PyMOL and cartoon views were applied.

Activating mutations of this receptor lead to hypocalcemia [38]. Interestingly, cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) demonstrated binding to an epitope also localized on the VFT domain of the receptor [45]. The VHH binds and stabilizes the inactive state of CaSR, thereby inhibiting its signaling. In addition, Cui and colleagues demonstrated that this VHH enhances the inhibitory effects of other CaSR antagonists, notably including a small molecule negative allosteric modulator [45].

LGICs are transmembrane proteins that regulate ion flux inside and outside of the cell. They constitute the second largest target class for treatments [37,46]. The acetylcholine receptor (AChR) is one of the most extensively characterized receptors in the context of allostery, despite the fact that only small molecule allosteric modulators have been reported [47]. Recently, Corringer's group identified a VHH that acts as a positive allosteric modulator of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR [48]. Their cryo-EM structure revealed that this VHH stabilizes the agonist-bound conformation and potentiates the acetylcholine-elicited currents [49]. These studies offer promises for a novel approach to targeting LGICs with VHHs.

Another compelling example of allosteric modulation of an LGIC is depicted by an antibody against the *N*-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) receptor: GluN2B [50]. This antibody exclusively stabilizes and locks the inactive conformation of the GluN1–GluN2B assembly, thereby abolishing its functions [50]. Through MD simulations, Tajima and colleagues highlighted long-range allosteric communications upon antibody binding, shifting the population of the receptor in favor of an inactive conformational state [50]. This study emphasizes the importance of validating allosteric communications using computational methods for a comprehensive understanding of how antibodies act allosterically.

In conclusion, GPCRs and LGICs undergo major conformational changes between active and inactive states due to allosteric perturbations. This dynamic nature makes them particularly suitable targets of antibodies exhibiting an allosteric mode of action.

LRRK2, ENPP1, IL-18R β : a new pharmacology

Antibodies acting at an allosteric site can modulate a protein's signaling, which may be dysregulated in several diseases. Breakthrough findings to treat degenerative diseases, cancer, and autoimmune conditions have emerged, highlighting a new pharmacology to regulate these target proteins. Leucine-rich repeat kinase 2 (LRRK2) is a large multidomain protein kinase that plays a crucial role in various cellular processes; mutations in this protein are the leading cause of the inherited form of Parkinson's disease [51]. The primary focus of LRRK2 treatment has been on competitive inhibitors, which demonstrate poor specificity for LRRK2 [51]. Singh and colleagues aimed to discover VHHs against various portions of LRRK2 [52]. They combined immunizations and screening to bias the antibody discovery process toward antibodies exhibiting an allosteric mode of action. Interestingly, a panel of allosteric VHHs were identified [52]. By protein crosslinking, these binding residues were mapped outside of the active site, demonstrating that VHHs stabilize an inactive conformation of LRRK2. These findings highlight the potential of exploiting allosteric sites to develop new LRRK2-targeting drugs that modulate its activities.

Recently, a comprehensive study detailed the first identification of a VHH that targets and inhibits ectodomain phosphatase/phosphodiesterase-1 (ENPP1), an **immune checkpoint** overexpressed in cancer [53]. Solomon and colleagues obtained a cryo-EM structure to confirm binding to a cryptic allosteric site located near the hydrolase active site [54]. Along with mutagenesis studies, they identified critical distinct binding residues that modulate substrate-specific inhibition of ENPP1 [54]. This VHH is the first **biologic** inhibitor reported for ENPP1, revealing new mechanistic insights into allosteric inhibition. This breakthrough finding facilitated the engineering and exploration of various

antibody formats, including a bispecific targeting PD-L1, another immune checkpoint. This format exhibited potent cellular activity, exhibiting greater specificity compared with small molecules [54].

Interleukin receptors (IL-Rs) play a vital role in cellular communications and their dysregulation is implicated in inflammatory diseases and autoimmune disorders. Thus, blockade of interleukin signaling may offer significant therapeutic benefits. Liu and colleagues reported the development of a synthetic antibody that targets IL-18R β [55]. The authors obtained a crystal structure of the complex, revealing that the antibody binds to a site of IL-18R β that is distinct from the IL-18 binding site [55]. Antibody binding induced significant conformational changes of IL-18R β , which modified the binding sites of IL-18 and IL-18R α (Figure 2), thereby impeding the formation of the ternary complex IL-18/IL-18R α /IL-18R β and subsequent signaling [55].

Allosterism to thwart infections

Infectious diseases are caused by viruses, bacteria, fungi, and parasites. Targeting allosteric sites of viral or bacterial proteins offers significant advantages, as these sites tend to be less sensitive to mutations.

Noroviruses, for instance, are the leading cause of gastroenteritis epidemics worldwide [56]. These viruses can accumulate numerous mutations in their capsid protein and, despite tremendous efforts, no antibody-based treatment has yet been approved [56]. Interestingly, neutralizing epitopes have been identified outside of the attachment site and a panel of VHHS has been characterized [57]. Salmen and colleagues obtained a crystal structure of the VHH that recognizes the most capsid protein variants, revealing binding to an epitope located distant from the ligand-binding site (Figure 2) [58]. Biophysical assays and cryo-EM suggested that VHH binding alters the structural dynamics of the capsid, ultimately leading to disassembly [58]. These findings present a unique opportunity to target an allosterically active region of a virus, potentially impeding infection and facilitating destruction of the virus particle.

Infections can also arise from bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, which releases the powerful toxin staphylococcal enterotoxin B (SEB). Fan and colleagues recently identified an antibody from patients that targets a linear conserved epitope on SEB [59]. Their crystal structure revealed a binding site distant from the SEB receptors (MHC-II and TCR) [59]. Biochemical and cell-based assays demonstrated that this antibody negatively affects the binding of MHC-II and TCR to SEB, interfering with the formation of the ternary complex, indicating allosteric inhibition [59]. This antibody neutralized SEB-induced toxicity and bacterial infection both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, opening up a novel strategy to combat bacterial infections.

Allosteric agonist antibodies targeting the TNF receptor superfamily (TNFRSF)

Agonist antibodies that activate signaling have emerged as promising biologics to restore or enhance cellular signaling [60]. Many of these agonist antibodies target co-stimulatory receptors in the TNFRSF, a superfamily of cytokine receptors [60]. Interestingly, agonist antibodies acting at an allosteric site of these receptors have been discovered.

Among these receptors, 4-1BB, also known as CD137, is a promising target on T cells for cancer immunotherapy [61]. Urelumab, an agonist antibody targeting 4-1BB, binds to a site distal from the 4-1BB ligand (4-1BBL) site. It induces conformational changes within 4-1BB that alter its spatial orientation, resulting in a more bent appearance (Figure 2) [62]. Moreover, this antibody promotes receptor clustering, as shown by confocal imaging [62]. Urelumab induces a stronger activation of 4-1BB compared with other first-generation anti-4-1BB antibodies that compete with 4-1BBL [62].

In addition to an agonist effect, allosteric antibodies also allow natural recognition of the ligand, thereby giving the possibility of an enhanced-targeting approach. OX40, another member of the TNFRSF, has also been reported to be allosterically modulated by an antibody [63]. The rationale for an allosteric anti-OX40 antibody was an increase of efficacy associated with an activation of OX40 without impairing the recognition of its natural ligand, OX40L [63]. Cocrystal structure revealed that the antibody binds to the opposite face of OX40 as OX40L, on a proximal epitope [63]. In preclinical models, this antibody has been reported to promote IL-2 secretion, thus increasing T cell proliferation.

Antibodies that act at an allosteric site can function as agonist antibodies, activating the signaling of co-receptors in the TNFRSF. This activation is not only dictated by the targeted epitope but can also be enhanced by isotype choice. Notably, the IgG2 format, which is less flexible than other IgGs, suggests additional communications between an antibody and its cognate target protein (Box 2).

Box 2. Hinge importance for agonistic properties

Yang and colleagues have discussed how different IgG subclasses, despite having identical variable regions, can exhibit different functional properties due to variations in their constant regions [97]. These differences can affect antigen-binding affinities, specificities, and effector functions. The hinge is the central part of antibodies, providing flexibility and facilitating communication within the antibody structure. The IgG2 format possesses an additional disulfide bond in its hinge region compared with the IgG1 format, which increases its rigidity. White and colleagues demonstrated that the IgG2 format imparts agonistic properties for multiple targets in the TNFRSF [98]. Yu and colleagues further demonstrated that a switch of functions, specifically a flip-flop between agonist and antagonist activities, is observed when modifying the isotype of antibodies targeting CD40, another member of the TNFRSF [99]. An antagonist anti-CD40 antibody could be modified to a super agonist by employing the IgG2 format, whose potency surpassed that of other agonist antibodies in *in vitro* studies [99]. Thus, an inverse relationship between hinge flexibility and agonistic properties is emerging (Figure 1). These findings constitute a paradigm shift in which both the targeted epitope and the antibody format play an equal role for the activity [100,101]. This makes it exceedingly difficult to understand the structure-activity relationship of antibodies and underlines the challenging nature of designing the full antibody structure.

Figure 1. Inverse relationship between hinge flexibility and agonistic properties. The IgG2 format possesses an additional disulfide bridge in its hinge region compared with the IgG1 format. This makes the IgG2 much more rigid and less flexible compared with the IgG1 format. The IgG2 format has been shown to have higher agonist properties when targeting the TNF receptor superfamily [98].

Emerging formats of allosteric antibodies

Successful modulation of target proteins through allosteric mechanisms is paving the way for the engineering of next-generation antibody formats.

In addition to T cell engagement, bispecific antibodies can also function as **natural killer (NK) cell engagers**. These molecules target a receptor on NK cells and a TAA on cancer cells. The group led by Zielonka described functional bispecific antibody formats targeting allosteric sites of NKp30 and EGFR (another RTK that has a similar structure to HER2) demonstrating engagement of NK cells and enhanced tumor activity [64,65]. Similar to T cells, NK cells can be redirected and activated independently of ligand binding.

Degrader–antibody conjugates (DACs) constitute an emerging format. DACs are antibodies conjugated to a **proteolysis-targeting chimera (PROTAC)**, a bifunctional small molecule [66]. DACs bind rapidly internalized, membrane-bound targets such as HER2 in order to release the PROTAC, which will initiate the targeted protein degradation [66]. Maneiro and colleagues reported the design of a DAC based on trastuzumab, an antibody that binds to an allosteric site of HER2 and promotes its internalization [67].

A new format of conditionally active antibodies, in which the activity is modulated by the environment to exert their potential, could enhance antibody specificity. Kellmann and colleagues reported a novel format consisting of a switchable antibody fragment based on the calmodulin linker [68]. The calmodulin conformational switch prompts conformational changes within the antibody fragment that influence antigen binding, making this format a supra-assembly that can be allosterically modulated. Another promising format has recently emerged: conditionally active **chimeric antigen receptor T cells (CAR T cells)**. Park and colleagues engineered conditionally active CAR T cells, in which the binding affinity to a target antigen is modulated by small molecules [69]. Toward precision medicines, these examples present a novel therapeutic approach to regulate antibody activity in patients through an allosteric mechanism.

Allosteric tool antibodies: moving beyond therapeutic application

The exploration of allosteric antibodies holds great promise for future therapeutic development, potentially leading to more effective and targeted treatments. Such allosteric antibodies are a groundbreaking advancement in drug discovery, offering a unique mechanism for modulating protein functions. While their therapeutic applications are well-documented, these antibodies could also serve as invaluable tools in the broader context of drug discovery.

Support for high-throughput screening

The stabilization of protein conformation is a crucial technique in medicinal chemistry, significantly contributing to the discovery of small molecules through **high-throughput screening (HTS)**. Recently, researchers at Genentech reported the discovery of antibodies that bind and stabilize a special conformation of KRAS, similar to that induced by approved anti-KRAS small molecules [70]. KRAS is an intracellular protein that is dysregulated in cancers [71]. While traditionally inaccessible for therapeutic antibodies, it remains a primary target for small molecules. For a long time, KRAS was considered undruggable until the identification and exploitation of a conformational pocket [71]. By capturing this unique conformation, these antibodies facilitate HTS and improve the discovery rates of novel therapeutic compounds. Similarly, ConfoTherapeutics has developed its proprietary ConfoBodies platform, which utilizes conformation-stabilizing VHHs to support HTS of small molecules targeting GPCRs [72]. These ConfoBodies selectively stabilize either the active or inactive conformer of GPCRs [72].

Chaperones for structural studies

Conformational changes enable researchers to characterize disordered regions of various target proteins. Historically, the stabilization of protein conformation was performed by co-crystallization with fragment antigen binding (Fab). Nowadays, smaller antibody fragments such as VHHs play a crucial role in studying complex proteins such as GPCRs [73,74] and are essential for obtaining high-resolution structures, particularly for capturing unique conformations. Additionally, an antibody targeting TNF has also been reported. This antibody binds to an allosteric site of TNF and contributes to the elucidation of the structure of the TNF–TNFR1 complex, thereby giving insight into its dynamics [75].

In conclusion, allosteric antibodies are not only valuable therapeutic compounds but also powerful tools in drug discovery. Their ability to stabilize specific protein conformations enhances HTS and facilitates structural studies. Their role in advancing medicinal chemistry and structural biology will expand toward a better understanding of the mechanism of action of compounds.

Future directions to design allosteric antibodies

One of the main challenges in the discovery of allosteric antibodies is their identification, which is mostly due to serendipity, despite some groups proposing biased experimental approaches to favor allosteric antibodies [52,76,77]. However, recent advances in computational structural biology have significantly enhanced our ability to identify relevant allosteric sites. These computational methods can be coupled with the initial steps of *de novo* antibody design, providing a more systematic approach to developing allosteric antibodies.

Allosteric sites identification

Myriad computational methods are available for the identification of allosteric sites [78–80]. However, traditional methods primarily focus on identifying pockets where small molecules can bind. Protein–protein interactions, such as antibody–antigen interfaces, due to their dynamic nature and large size, require more general approaches.

Going beyond the search for pockets, a more general approach is to identify allosteric networks in the target protein and the corresponding communications between key regions. This theoretical understanding emerges from the evolutionary conservatism of allosteric communications in proteins despite their variability of structure and sequence [81]. For instance, by evaluating the energetics and causal relationships between different regions of target proteins in response to binding events and mutations, the structure-based statistical model of allostery (SBSMMA) [82–84] provides a framework for the identification of allosteric epitopes. Incorporated in the AlloSigMA webserver [85,86], the SBSMMA allows for the detection of allosterically active regions via perturbations of the orthosteric site of target proteins (i.e., reverse perturbation method) [87,88], which can potentially achieve great predictive power in combination with **machine learning (ML)** methods [89].

Toward *de novo* designing allosteric antibodies

Understanding of protein regulation combined with recent breakthroughs in protein structure prediction offers a great opportunity in designing an antibody that would target a given allosteric site. Recent advancements in **artificial intelligence (AI)** and computational structural biology have demonstrated that ML algorithms can be leveraged to potentially *de novo* generate antibody sequences optimized for binding affinity and specificity [90–93].

Better understanding of allosteric communications in a protein would also benefit the design of antibodies, which are themselves highly dynamic. Zhao and colleagues investigated the impact

of antigen binding on the conformation of antibodies using MD simulations [94,95]. The observed populations shift toward conformations more favorable for effector functions [94]; this was also confirmed experimentally [96]. These communications within the antibody structure offer a novel understanding of antibody functionality that should be considered entirely and not solely focused on their paratope.

Taken together, these advanced computational methods are expected to enable researchers to effectively tailor antibodies toward targeting specific allosteric sites, potentially improving therapeutic outcomes and reducing off-target effects.

Concluding remarks and future perspectives

It has been almost 40 years since the first antibody, muromonab-CD3, was approved, and antibodies have since become the fastest growing class of biologics. Recent studies strongly support the emerging opportunities associated with antibodies to modulate a target protein allosterically. Whereas small molecules and peptides were first reported as allosteric modulators [6], allosteric antibodies are offering a novel toolbox to target disease-relevant proteins. Because of their better selectivity profiles, allosteric antibodies could become a preferred modality for some antibody-undruggable targets, including GPCRs, LGICs, or other enzymes such as LRRK2 or ENPP1. In addition, their ability to bind extracellularly and promote the internalization of some of their cognate targets makes them very suitable for the engineering of various formats such as ADCs and DACs. By exploiting the conformational dynamics of the target protein, more applications could arise (see [Outstanding questions](#)).

Apart from their application as therapeutics, allosteric antibodies were also developed as tools to support HTS of small molecules. The identification of allosteric networks and communications is progressing along with the development of modern computational methods. The remaining challenge would be the directed design of allosteric antibodies. As such, the design of allosteric antibodies must be approached with meticulous consideration of the full conformational dynamics of both the target protein and the antibody.

Allostery, often considered as the second secret of life, is emerging as the not-so-secret modulatory activity of antibodies.

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Declaration of interests

L.F., E.G., and S.B. are employees of Merck Healthcare KGaA. H.K. states no conflict of interest.

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Outstanding questions

Will allosteric sites/epitopes become the preferred target sites for antibody discovery?

What new type of allosteric antibodies will emerge?

How can AI improve the current computational methods to predict antibody-druggable allosteric sites?

How can we understand the structure–activity relationship (SAR) of allosteric antibodies?

How far are we from specifically designing a high affinity antibody targeting a given allosteric site of a target protein?

Are there intrinsic limitations for proteins to be regulated by an allosteric antibody?

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